

Gas-Phase Deposited Plasmonic NPs Supported on 3D-Graphene/Nickel Foam for Highly Sensitive SERS detection

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Abstract

In this work, we proposed a novel three-dimensional (3D) plasmonic nanostructure based on porous Graphene/Nickel foam (GNF) and gas-phase deposited Ag nanoparticles (NPs)NP. Ag NPs with high density were directly deposited on the surface of 3D GNF by performing a novel cluster beam deposition approach. In comparison with traditional Ag substrate (SiO₂/Ag), such hot-spots enriched 3D nanostructure showed extremely high electromagnetic field enhancement under incident light irradiation which could be used as a sensitive chemical sensor based on Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS). The experimental results demonstrated that the proposed nanostructure showed superior SERS performance in terms of Raman signal reproducibility and sensitivity for the probe molecules. 3D full-wave simulation showed that the enhanced SERS performance in this 3D hierarchical plasmonic nanostructure was mainly obtained from the hot-spots between Ag NPs and the near-field coupling between Ag NPs and GNF scaffolds. This work can provide a novel assembled SERS substrate as a SERS-based chemical sensor in practical applications.

Key words: plasmonic, cluster beam, nanoparticle, graphene, surface enhanced Raman

1 Introduction

The design and fabrication of metallic nanostructures for large electric field enhancement have become increasingly important over the last few years with the aim to enhance the performance in nanophotonic devices, such as light emission devices¹, energy harvesting devices² and optically chemical sensors based on Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS)³. Such nanostructures could concentrate light into an ultra-small scale and produce additional high local-field intensities; this phenomenon is called localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) and the ultra-small scale of the nanostructures are often called “hot-spots”⁴. SERS technique based on electromagnetic field enhancement is one of the most successful attempts in utilizing LSPR properties of metallic nanostructures in the detection of environmental pollutants, drugs and pesticides due to its high sensitivity and fingerprint features⁵. Up to now, various nanostructures could hold “hot-spots” have been developed including nanospheres⁶, nanocubes⁷, nanostars⁸ and nanoflowers⁹ to generate local field enhancement and thus improve the sensitivity of the SERS detection. However, the number of “hot-spots” generated from these simple nanostructures is rather limited, the sensitive of Raman signal is too low to fulfil a robust SERS identification of chemicals in real environment application. Therefore, the evolution of SERS as a powerful analytic technique still faces several challenges including how to produce a SERS substrate with a large number of “hot-spots” and how to place the probe molecules into the “hot-spots” effectively^{5b}.

Recently, various complex nanostructures have been proposed to construct SERS substrates

with a large number of hot-spots, such as NP-over-mirror structure¹⁰, NP matrix¹¹ and NP/nanorod hierarchical nanostructures¹². These nanostructures with the aim to further enhance the SERS sensitivity through the coupling between plasmons of various shapes, sizes, or materials, or heterogeneous plasmonic coupling. In addition, the traditional SERS substrates always consist of 2D arrays of metallic nanostructures, “hot-spots” formed in these nanostructures are limited to a single Cartesian plane¹³. In comparison with traditional 2D SERS substrate, the complex plasmonic nanostructures are pursued to increase the number and utility of “hot-spots” in all three dimensions such that SERS active regions are not limited to a single Cartesian plane^{5b, 11, 13-14}. Many fabrication strategies have been put forward to construct complex 3D SERS active substrates, such as direct chemical growth¹⁵, chemical etching¹⁶, electron beam lithography¹⁷ and solvent-assisted printing¹⁸. However, most of the approaches for high volume manufacturing of these 3D “hot-spots” are challenging due to lack of fabrication techniques that satisfy high throughput, low cost, and sufficient reproducibility.

Herein, we create a novel 3D hierarchical SERS-active substrate with high adsorptivity, sensitivity and reproducibility by integrating 3D Graphene/Nickel foam (GNF) and gas-phase deposited Ag NPs. Graphene has attracted intense interest in SERS area because of the ability of graphene to absorb and concentrate target molecules which makes it an attractive candidate for plasmonic sensing applications¹⁹. In this work, Ag NPs formed in a novel gas-phase cluster source were directly deposited on the surface of graphene obtained by template-directed chemical vapour deposition on the nickel foam. We experimentally and theoretically demonstrate a significant near-field enhancement, as well as a large number of “hot-spots” can be obtained in this structure, which is due to the 3D architecture can support multiple plasmonic couplings between the disordered Ag NPs as well as between the Ag NP and GNF. By detecting R6G molecules, the 3D GNF/Ag plasmonic structures display excellent SERS activity, reproducibility and homogeneity.

2 Experimental and numerical calculations section

2.1 Fabrication of Graphene foam

Details of the synthesis process of the 3D Graphene composite have been reported in our previous work²⁰. Briefly, the 3D graphene foams with a continuous single and few-layer graphene were synthesized by chemical vapour deposition. In this fabrication, a porous nickel foam (NF) with 3D interconnected branches was used as a template, and the nickel template was put into quartz tubular furnace and heated to 1000 °C about 10 min under H₂ and Ar atmosphere for pretreatment. After that, ethanol as the carbon source was passed into the furnace with a mixed gas of H₂ and Ar as the carrier gas. The deposition was maintained at standard ambient pressure for 20 min, and then the samples were rapidly cooled to room temperature at a rate of 100°C min⁻¹.

2.2 Fabrication of 3D GNF/Ag structure

In the fabrication of 3D GNF/Ag structure, the Ag NPs were directly deposited on the surface of GNF by performing a home-made gas-phase cluster beam deposition, the details of cluster beam deposition technique can be found elsewhere²¹. The gas-phase cluster beam deposition system consists of a magnetron sputtering cluster source, a differential vacuum system and a deposition chamber, as shown in **Figure 1(a)**. An Ag plate (diameter 50 mm) with high purity (99.999%) was used as the target, a DC power source was used as a power supply and Ar was used as both sputtering and buffer gas. Sputtered Ag atoms lost energy by colliding with the cooled argon gas in the aggregation tube and formed NPs. The NPs were swept by the gas stream into high vacuum

through a nozzle and skimmer, forming a collimated NP beam with a high speed of ~ 1 km/s. Thus, the NPs deposited and stuck on the GNF surface firmly. During the deposition, the substrate holder was keeping rotating clockwise and counter-clockwise alternatively, which could avoid non-uniform deposition on the branch surface of the graphene foam. The deposition was carried out at a rate of 1.0 ± 0.1 Å/s for 15 min. In situ annealing was carried out for 10 min at 150 °C, after the deposition. The morphology of the GNF/Ag structures was characterized by performing scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

2.3 SERS characterization

The Raman spectra are recorded from an upright-configured confocal microscopy (NT-MDA NTEGRA SPECTRA) with a 473 nm laser. Rhodamine 6G (R6G) (purchased from Sigma-Aldrich) was used as the probe molecule and dissolved in ethanol to prepare a solution with different concentrations. For Raman measurements, SERS substrates were soaked in the R6G-ethanol solution for 30 min and then removed them from the solution vertically, washed by ethanol and then dried under flowing N_2 . For quantitative estimation of the enhancement factor of the 3D GNF/Ag nanostructure, a 100 mM R6G-in-methanol solution was used to prepare a reference sample. For the reference sample, a drop (around 10 μ L) of 100 mM R6G-in-methanol solution was dispersed onto a flat surface of silica slice.

2.4. Numerical calculations

Finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) method calculations with commercial software (FDTD solution, Lumerical Inc.) are used to simulate the linear response of GNF/Ag nanostructure. A conformal mesh with size down to 0.5 nm (x, y and z directions) was used. The optical constants of Ni and Ag were taken from E. Palik²² at the wavelength of 473 nm. The refractive index of SiO_2 was set to a constant of 1.4. Graphene can be considered as an anisotropic material, and the surface conductivity σ_g can be expressed as²³:

$$\sigma_g = \frac{2e^2 k_B T}{\pi \hbar^2} \frac{i}{\omega + i\tau^{-1}} \ln \left[2 \cosh \left(\frac{E_F}{2k_B T} \right) \right] + \frac{e^2}{4\hbar} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \arctan \left(\frac{\hbar\omega - 2E_F}{2k_B T} \right) \right] - \frac{i}{2\pi} \ln \frac{(\hbar\omega + 2E_F)^2}{(\hbar\omega - 2E_F)^2 + 4(k_B T)^2} \right]$$

where e is the charge of an electron, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the operation temperature, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, ω is the angular frequency of the incidence light, τ is the relaxation time and E_F is the Fermi energy. Perfectly matched layer (PML) boundary condition was applied for z-direction, while periodic boundary condition was set for x and y directions of the FDTD simulation region. The amplitude $|E_0|$ of incident light was 1.

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 1. (a) Schematically illustration of gas-phase cluster beam deposition system. (b) SEM image of 3D GNF/Ag nanostructure. (c) SEM image of a branch of the GNF/Ag nanostructure. (d) High magnification image of a GNF/Ag branch. (e) SEM image of Ag NPs on GNF structure. (f) Size distribution of Ag NPs deposited on the surface of GNF.

In Figure 1 (b), the SEM image shows the surface morphology of the GNF/Ag structure. The monolithic and porous 3D graphene architecture can be clearly observed in Figure 1(b). From the high magnification SEM images showed in Figure 1 (c) and (d), we can clearly find that the Ag NPs are uniformly deposited on the surface of graphene foam. By counting about 300 Ag NPs from SEM image (Figure 1(e)), we statistically obtain the size distribution of Ag NPs and the corresponding size-distribution histogram is shown in Figure 1(f), the average size of the Ag NPs is about 70 nm. In addition, it can be found from the SEM image that the Ag NPs are disorderly and closely packed together; the very dense distribution of Ag NPs is very beneficial to their coupling for further enhancing the near-field intensity.

The quality of as-deposited GNF was characterized by Raman spectroscopy, as shown in Figure 2. From the Raman spectrum, it can be found that the two characteristic peaks of graphene at 1580 cm^{-1} (G-band) and 2727 cm^{-1} (2D-band) are evident. Particularly, the 2D peak around 2727 cm^{-1} is the signature of monolayer graphene with a single band electronic dispersion^{19a}. The Raman D-band (at 1350 cm^{-1}) is originated from the disordered carbon in graphene, and its intensity indicates the density of defects in the as-grown graphene film. Therefore, in the Raman spectrum, the absence of a D band at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Raman spectrum indicates that the 3D GNF is of high quality with few defects. The layer number of the as-deposited graphene can be confirmed by extracting the integrated intensity ratio of G and 2D bands (I_G/I_{2D}) in the Raman spectrum²⁴. In Figure 2, the shape of the 2D band and the intensity ratio between the 2D and the G bands prove that the 3D GNF is composed of few-layer or multilayer graphene sheets. Because I_G increases monotonically with the increasing graphene thickness whereas I_{2D} is relatively stable, I_G/I_{2D} scales linearly with the number of graphene layers (up to 4 layers).

Figure 2. Typical Raman spectrum measured from the as-deposited GNF.

To better understand the plasmonic and field enhancement properties of the 3D GNF/Ag structure, FDTD simulations were performed to calculate the electric field distributions. The models used in the simulation can be found in Figure 3(a). For comparison, Ag NP with the size of 70 nm was placed on GNF and SiO₂ substrate, respectively. The incident wavelength was set to 473 nm to match the pump laser in the SERS measurements. In the GNF/Ag structure, Ag NP and Ni separated by several layers of graphene, the thickness of graphene was set to 8 nm.

For the case of GNF/Ag structure, we can find from the field distribution in Figure 3 (b) that the hot-spot appears to be around the region of graphene nanospacer, which is similar with the NP-over-mirror structure reported previously^{10, 25}. We note that the graphene exhibits good penetrability so that the electric field can efficiently pass through the several layers graphene nanospacer. In addition, in comparison to the case of Ag NP on silica (Figure 3(d) and (e)), the electric field intensity around the Ag NP in GNF/Ag structure increases by leaps and bounds, which can attribute to intense resonant coupling phenomenon between Ag NP and nickel substrate with only nanoscale-level interval (thickness of several layers of graphene). The theoretical simulation was also conducted to study the effect of the plasmonic coupling of inter-Ag NPs to field enhancement. As shown in Figure 3 (f) and (g), we note that the field enhancement not only generate from the coupling between Ag NP and GNF/Ni substrate, but also from the plasmonic coupling of inter-particles, which largely increasing the number of “hot-spots” as well as the intensity of electric field. Thus, our theoretical results reveal a greater field enhancement for the 3D GNF/Ag system due to multiple plasmonic coupling.

Figure 3 (a) FDTD simulation model of GNF/Ag nanostructure. Electric field distributions of the single Ag NP/GNF system in x-z plane (b) and x-y plane (plane across the kissing point of Ag NP and graphene) (c). Electric field distributions of the single Ag NP/SiO₂ system in x-z plane (d) and x-y plane (plane across the kissing point of Ag NP and SiO₂ substrate) (e). The cross-sectional near field profile of Ag NP-Ag NP/GNF system (f) and Ag NP-Ag NP/SiO₂ system (g).

Regarding the potential applications of the sample in the chemical sensor, we further investigate the sensing capability of as-prepared GNF/Ag structures in detecting a typical dye R6G as a probe molecule using SERS technique. For comparison, we study the SERS response of the two structures: GNF/Ag structure and SiO₂/Ag structure. Figure 4 (a) shows the SERS spectra of R6G from two structures including GNF/Ag case and SiO₂/Ag case. The position of the characteristic peaks including 613, 775, 1187, 1309, 1360, 1506, 1569 and 1648 cm⁻¹ attributed to R6G generally agrees with that reported previously^{19a, 26}. Compared the Raman signal of the two structures, we find that the Raman intensity of R6G is enhanced by introducing GNF on the bottom of Ag NPs. These results indicate that the 3D GNF/Ag structure can largely improve the SERS performance by building multiple plasmonic modes between the different units in the structure, thus increasing both the number of “hot-spots” and the intensity of electric field, which is basically an agreement with the FDTD simulation results. In addition, according to the previously reported results, firstly, graphene could facilitate charge transfer between graphene and probe molecules, resulting in a vibration mode dependent enhancement. Secondly, aromatic molecules prefer to stack in parallel to the π -bonds of graphene through π - π stacking and lead to enhanced resonant energy transfer, which belongs to chemical enhancement mechanism^{26b, 27}.

Figure 4. (a) Comparison of R6G Raman signal from GNF/Ag structures and SiO_2/Ag structure. (b) Raman spectrum of as-deposited GNF (brown line); Raman spectra of R6G measured on GNF/Ag substrate, NF/Ag substrate, GNF substrate and SiO_2 substrate. (c) SERS mapping of vibration modes at 1360 cm^{-1} of R6G molecules at 10^{-6} M dispensed on the 3D GNF/Ag substrate. (d) The intensity distribution of the 1360 cm^{-1} peak in a branch from the GNF/Ag substrate. The inset shows the SEM image of the measured branch.

We estimate the enhancement performance of the proposed 3D GNF/Ag structure by detecting the Raman signals from 3D GNF/Ag substrate and reference substrate under same conditions, as shown in Figure 4(b). Compared with the reference sample, the Raman signal on 3D substrate is largely enhanced and this indicates that the 3D GNF/Ag structure could offer a significant enhancement to improve the sensitivity in effective molecule detection. On the other hand, we also investigated the SERS signals obtained from NF/Ag-R6G substrate and GNF-R6G substrate, as shown in Figure 4(b). The 3D GNF/Ag plasmonic nanostructure generated a R6G SERS signal that was 1.8 times the signal generated at the NF/Ag plasmonic nanostructures, this indicates that graphene plays a very important role in local field enhancement—supporting intense resonant coupling between Ag NP and nickel substrate. However, enhanced SERS signal could not be obtained on the surface of pure graphene, as shown in Figure 4 (b). Not only limited to provide plasmonic coupling of NPs and Ni substrate, the Ni foam also produces a multiple cascaded amplification process, which is due to the 3D porous morphology could support multiple interfaces of AgNP/Graphene. In addition, 3D GNF/Ag plasmonic structure could increase the number and utility of “hot-spots” in all three dimensions such that SERS active regions are not limited to a single Cartesian plane.

SERS is an important analytical method that can be used to obtain fingerprint information of the target molecule. The uniformity and reproducibility of the active substrate are crucial for using

SERS in real-life applications. We further investigate the uniformity and reproducibility of the 3D GNF/Ag substrates, Raman mapping was performed in the sample-scanning mode with a step of 0.5 μm per point and a dwell time of 0.5s per point. We only choose a branch of the 3D GNF/Ag structure to scan the Raman mapping due to the microscale porous structure of the foam, as shown in Figure 4 (c). The panel in Figure 4 (c) illustrates the measured rectangular region (30 μm \times 30 μm) with the brightness of the grid being proportional to the signal intensity at 1360 cm^{-1} . It can be clearly found that the brightness of the lower part of the mapping is sharply decreased, which means the laser spots was away from the branch during the scanning, as shown in the inset of Figure 4 (c). The corresponding Raman spectra along the marked line of the mapping area are also shown in Figure 4 (d). Through the intensity distribution we can quantitatively evaluate the SERS reproducibility, the relative standard deviation (RSD, the ratio of standard deviation to the mean) of the Raman intensity is also calculated about 4.3%, which are consistently much less than 20%, further indicating the excellent homogeneity of Raman signal on the 3D GNF/Ag nanostructure.

4 Conclusion

In summary, we have proposed and prepared a novel GNF/Ag system by combining and 3D-graphene foam and highly dense and disordered gas-phase deposited Ag NPs. The deposited Ag NPs and Nickle scaffold were well separated well-prepared several layers of graphene. Our results show that the 3D GNF/Ag system offers can generate a number of plasmonic “hot-spots” and offer tremendous near-field enhancement in comparison to the traditional Ag NP plasmonic SERS substrates. Particularly, the strong electric field enhancement at the nanopspacer additional chemical enhancement from graphene offers a very useful opportunity for the detection of absorbed molecules by SERS technique. Our experimental and theoretical results show that the enhancement can be explained due to multiple plasmonic couplings between Ag NPs as well as between the Ag NP and graphene/Ni foam. By using R6G molecules as a probe, the 3D GNF/Ag foam structures display excellent SERS activity. Moreover, the 3D GNF/Ag SERS substrate possessed excellent reproducibility and homogeneity (RSD < 10%), and this cluster beam technique could exceed some technical barriers and be scaled up for commercialization in analytical science and related fields.

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